

D9.2: Data for Case Studies

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WP 9, T 9.2

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Technical references

Project Acronym	DISTENDER
Project Title	Developing STRatEgies by integrating mitigation, aDaptation and participation to climate change Risks
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Project Duration	June 2022 – November 2025 (42 months)

Deliverable No.	D9.2
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 9 – Case studies
Task	T9.2 – Data requirements
Lead beneficiary	1. (UPM)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	(KVC), (CEH)
Due date of deliverable	31 may 2023
Actual submission date	31 may 2023

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	01/04/2023	UPM	Roberto San José
2.0	01/05/2023	UPM	Roberto San José
3.0	22/05/2023	UPM	Roberto San José

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List of abbreviations

CC: Climate Change
CCS Core Case Study
EU European Union
IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
SSP Shared Socioeconomic Pathway

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable D9.2 is an important milestone in the DISTENDER project that marks the completion of T9.2. The main objective of this task was to collect the required data from the core case studies to enable the modelling teams in WP4, WP5, and WP7 to perform their simulations optimally from the perspective of the case studies (WP9). This task was divided into two sub-tasks to ensure the efficient and effective collection of data.

In the first sub-task, the modelling partners provided a list of data required from the core case studies to perform their simulations. This data was specific to the modelling tools used in each sector, including air quality, urban heat, agriculture, energy, water, and economy. The partners were also required to provide information on the characteristics of their data, such as units, temporal and spatial resolution, spatial data type, time periods, and formats. They were also asked to specify the source of the data, whether it could be produced by other models, available data sources, or observations that should be provided by the core case studies.

Once T9.2 had gathered all the necessary information from the modelling partners, the next step was to generate a uniform and homogeneous data request (table and documentation) that would avoid duplication of requests and facilitate the provision of data by the core case studies. The data was then uploaded to the DISTENDER SFTP server, following the indications and recommendations of the deliverable D1.2 Data Management Plan I.

In conclusion, the completion of task T9.2 and the delivery of the D9.2 deliverable marked an important milestone in the DISTENDER project, ensuring that the modelling teams had the necessary data to perform their simulations optimally. The efficient collection and provision of data was crucial for the success of the project, and important work of the CCS partners provided a useful dataset collection.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 General context

DISTENDER is a Horizon Europe project which aims to provide a reference methodology that facilitates the implementation of adaptation and mitigation strategies to Climate Change (CC) in a series of European case studies. To that end, bottom-up and top-down approaches are carried out into a cross-sectorial framework which considers interactions between adaptation and mitigation actions in sectors such as agriculture, health and well-being, energy, water, biodiversity, forestry, transport or urban planning. The methodology of DISTENDER combines quantitative (e.g., sophisticated models and tools) and qualitative analyses (e.g., participatory approaches) involving relevant stakeholders with the ultimate goal to understand the interactions, synergies and trade-offs between adaptation and mitigation strategies in the selected case studies under future climate conditions assuming different socio-economic scenarios.

As to the quantitative part, in DISTENDER, the levels of uncertainty and robustness of the results obtained from the simulations performed (therefore, strategies) are assessed through several modelling rounds. In particular, the holistic approach of the project allows us to us conduct tailor-made simulations of the future climate for the different case studies, as well as to simulate the impacts and risks posed by the future climate conditions over a wide range of sectors under different socio-economic scenarios. Specifically, a combination of dynamical and statistical downscaling of the climate and of atmospheric pollution is being conducted in WP4 (Downscaling climate scenarios) for each case study. For this, state-of-the-art meteorological and air quality models are adopted. Additionally, impact models are used in WP5 (Risk and vulnerability assessment) to evaluate the effects of projected climate conditions on multiple sectors: agriculture, air quality, biodiversity, buildings, energy, health, transport and water management. Furthermore, a set of models will be used to perform an economic evaluation of the adaptation and mitigation strategies envisaged by the WP7 (Cost-benefits evaluation and impacts).

In DISTENDER there are a total of 11 case studies participating. These have been chosen due to their diversity in terms of e.g., sectors, scale, climate impacts, environmental, socioeconomic and cultural factors and climate policy goals. This ensures that the final products are complete and the methodology replicable in other European regions. The case studies are divided into two categories: core (5 of them) and follower (the other 6) case studies. Whilst the methodology will be implemented in the core case studies (CCSs), the followers have the role of learning the methodology developed in CCSs. In this context, the involvement of the partners from the case studies and related stakeholders is crucial for the success of the project. The reason for this is that their inputs and feedback in dedicated activities is required for a participative implementation of the project which, in turn, is required to launch a battery of tailor-made, understandable results and/or recommendations that can be used by policy makers to plan adaptation and mitigation strategies. Thus, the partners from the case studies have a very active role since the beginning of the project.

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1.2 Work Package 9 (Case Studies) and Task 9.2: General objectives

In a generic way, in terms of tasks, the main role of the WP9 is (i) to provide an initial, complete definition of the case studies characteristics in order to compile relevant information to be used by other WPs in the implementation of their respective tasks; (ii) to collect the data needed for the modelling partners to run their models and tools and (iii) to conduct a participatory final evaluation of the process and outcomes reached. In addition to that, an essential role of this WP consists of facilitating the communication between the partners from the case studies and the rest of the scientific partners of the project. This promotes an optimal implementation of the multiple tasks in which the case studies are involved, which could be hampered due to the differences in the backgrounds of the partners from the case studies (mostly policy makers) and the rest of the scientific partners from the consortium. Therefore, the WP9 is in direct communication with the partners from many other WPs in which the contribution of the case studies is key due to the participative nature of the project e.g., WP2: Co-creation and stakeholder engagement, WP3: Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios, WP4: downscaling climate scenarios, WP5: Risk and vulnerability assessment or WP6: Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies.

This deliverable focuses on the description of Task 9.2 “Data requirements”, led by the UPM. In other words, the aim of this task is to define and collect the required data from the core case studies to optimally perform the simulations by the modelling teams (WP4, WP5, WP7). To achieve this, two sub-tasks which are explained in detail in Section 2 and 3, were performed. At first stage, the partners from the modelling teams specified the data required from the core case studies in order to perform their simulations. On the other hand, the partners from the core case studies were given instructions as to which data to provide, as well as how to deliver it. It should be noted that the simulations were exclusively performed in the core case studies and that followers did not have to provide any data.

1.3 Presentation of the case studies

As stated above, the participating case studies in DISTENDER can be divided into core and follower case studies. In this sub-section we provide a brief description of the case studies with the focus being on the core ones using the information provided in Deliverable 9.1.

1.3.1 Core Case Studies

In DISTENDER there are 5 CCSs. These are located at different European countries and comprise different spatial scales, ranging from national level to urban level (see their geographical location in Figure 1):

Austria (BMK): this case study is the only one which participates at country level. The area of interest thus covers the entire Federal Republic of Austria, with a total surface of 83,858 km² and 8.9 million inhabitants (2020). The topography in the area includes the eastern Alps and the Danube region and the three main climate types there are Continental Pannonian, Alpine and Central European.

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North-East of The Netherlands (HUAS): this case study has a regional level and includes the provinces of Groningen, Friesland and Drenthe, which account for a total surface area of 11,200 km². The total population in these provinces is 1,741,932. The most remarkable topographic features of the area of interest rely in the presence of an artificially changed landscape due to the reclamation of land and hinterland subsidence. Also remarkable is the presence of the IJsselmeer Lake, which acts as a freshwater and flood buffer, through a technical system of dams, pumps and dikes. The climate in the area is Maritime.

South-West of the Iberian Peninsula (EURAF): this case study has a regional level, is the only one which covers two countries (Spain and Portugal) and includes an agroforestry system. Over the Spanish part, the Extremadura region covers 41,635.43 km² and has a population of 1,059,501 inhabitants (2021). The main features of Dehesas (in Extremadura) and Montados (in Portugal) is that they mainly consist of open canopy woodlands with interspersed patches of shrubs and with natural or cultivated grassland in the undercover, which are grazed by livestock. The climate is Mediterranean semi-arid to dry sub-humid with some oceanic influence.

Guimaraes (Portugal): this urban case study includes the municipality of Guimaraes, which is located in the north of Portugal, in the district of Braga. The municipality occupies about 241 km², is divided into 48 parishes and counts with a population of about 156,852 inhabitants (2021). As to topography, it includes a valley surrounded by hills, cut with three rivers. The climate in the territory is Temperate with Mediterranean characteristics and a strong Atlantic influence.

Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0): this case study, located in the north of Italy, covers a total surface area of 6,827 km² and has a population of about 2 million inhabitants, living in the city of Turin about 860.000 people (2021). Regarding topography, this is a heterogeneous territory, with dense urban areas to peri-urban areas, part of that is flat or hilly in the south and east. The climate is Temperate, Subcontinental in the Alps, becoming gradually temperate-cold and cold with altitude.

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Figure 1. Domains (boxes) covering the administrative boundaries of the Case Studies of DISTENDER (1: Austria; 2: North-East of the Netherlands; 3: South-West of the Iberian Peninsula; 4: Guimaraes; 5: Metropolitan City of Turin). The specific meaning of each colour box corresponds to the different modelling domains (Black box: domain for meteorological and hydrological models; Red box: domain where all modellers have to provide results; Green box: the areas with higher resolution in which all models have to produce results).

1.3.2 Follower Case Studies

The follower case studies that participate in DISTENDER are: Alcorcón (Spain), LVIV (Ukraine), Miskolc (Hungary), Nova Gorica (Slovenia), Gdansk (Poland) and Valencia (Spain).

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2 DATA REQUIREMENTS

DISTENDER is a comprehensive project in which various modelling tools across multiple sectors such as air quality, urban heat, agriculture, energy, water, and economy are used. In order to achieve this, the project requires specific data requirements depending on the model. For example, the air quality modelling tool required data on pollutant emissions, meteorological variables, and land use information. The urban heat modelling tool, on the other hand, required data on surface temperature, solar radiation, and building characteristics. The agricultural modelling tool needed data on crop types, soil properties, and irrigation practices. Similarly, the energy modelling tool required data on energy consumption patterns, building energy performance, and energy production capacities. The water modelling tool required data on precipitation, evapotranspiration, and groundwater recharge rates. Finally, the economic modelling tool required data on employment rates, GDP, and investment flows. Whilst climate data will be produced in DISTENDER, additional external data is required for the models. This information is specific for the area of the CCS, so datasets of the CCS will be provided by them with the support of the other WP9 partners.

When research is conducted in a specific study area, the reliance on accurate and reliable data cannot be overstated. In such cases, it is essential that the data is provided by partners who represent each respective study area, as they possess valuable knowledge about the local data sources from which to obtain the required information. These partners play a crucial role in ensuring that the data collected is both relevant and comprehensive. The unique characteristics of each CCS necessitate the inclusion of local partners in the data collection process. Local partners possess intimate familiarity with the area, including its geographical, environmental, and socio-economic attributes. Their expertise allows them to identify and access the most relevant local data sources, which may include government records, databases, surveys, and other pertinent repositories of information. By involving partners who represent each respective study area, researchers gain access to a wealth of localized knowledge and data sources that might otherwise be challenging to obtain. These partners act as conduits between the research team and the local community, facilitating the acquisition of data that accurately reflects the characteristics and dynamics of the study area. Moreover, local partners possess a deep understanding of the intricacies and challenges associated with data collection in their specific study areas. They are familiar with the potential limitations, biases, or inconsistencies that may arise, and can provide valuable insights and guidance to help mitigate these issues. Their expertise in navigating local bureaucratic processes, data collection protocols, and potential data gaps is invaluable for maintaining the overall integrity and reliability of the study.

To achieve a unified data collection, the first step taken by UPM (leader of T9.2) was to ask the modelling partners to describe the input data needed to run their models. The aim of this was to ensure that there was a clear understanding of the specific data requirements for each model. To this end, the modelling partners were asked to fill in an Excel sheet that was shared with them using the DISTENDER Share Point (example of the excel sheet is show in Figure 2). This allowed them to report on the data used in their models and served as a basis for a unified data collection.

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B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
Group of dataset	Short Name-Full name of the variable	Units	Temporal resolution	Source	Dimension	Spatial data type	Spatial extent	Horizontal resolution	Vertical resolution	Time Period	Format	Projection	Model/Tool Name
Spatial Data	Land use and land cover	None	One base year	Existing data, could be global	None	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	None	base year	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Soil map with chemical and physical characteristics	Depends on characteristic	One base year	Existing data, could be global	3D	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	multiple soil levels	base year	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Population density	pop. / ha	At least one base year	Existing data, could be global	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	None	base year	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Population density	pop. / ha	yearly	Modelled input	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	None	base year - 2050	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Context data for model runs	Population under different scenarios	total number	yearly	Existing data	None	None	Country	None	None	base year - 2050	csv	None	ICLUE
Context data for model runs	Land use under different scenarios	land use change in hectares / year	yearly	Existing data	None	None	Country	None	None	base year - 2050	csv	None	ICLUE
Context data for model runs	Gross Domestic Product	% change per year	yearly	Existing data	None	None	Country	None	None	base year - 2050	csv	None	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Road map/ accessibility/ travel distance	y/n	base year	Existing data	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	None	base year	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Spatial policies (protected areas, etc.)	None	base year and end year	Existing data	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	None	base year and 2050	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Digital Elevation Model	meters	base year	Existing data	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	None	base year	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Climate Data (length of growing season; Prec. etc.)	None	monthly, daily	Modelled input	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	1 km2 or higher	None	base year - 2050	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Mean monthly Temperature (average, min, max)	degrees C	monthly	Modelled input	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	10x10 km2	None	base year - 2050	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Total monthly Precipitation	mm/month	monthly	Modelled input	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	10x10 km2	None	base year - 2050	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Evapotranspiration	mm/month	monthly	Modelled input	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	10x10 km2	None	base year - 2050	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Spatial Data	Daily heavy Precipitation events	mm/day	daily	Modelled input	2D	Raster	CS or region/country	10x10 km2	None	base year - 2050	GIS compatible	Lat/Long or depends on case study	ICLUE
Global and regional climate datasets	U-Component of Wind	m/s	6-hourly	Modelling	2D	Raster	Global/regiona l	18 or higher	Multiple pressure levels	2016-2050	Netcdf	Lat/Lon	{10 CMI/6 models + 10 EURO-CORDEX} x (Mist + 43SP) 110 CMI/6

Figure 2. Example of the table about the input data requirements to fill out by the “modelling partners”.

The modelling partners were asked to provide the name of the variables required to run their respective models, as well as additional information regarding the data characteristics. This additional information included e.g. the units of measurement, temporal and spatial resolution, spatial data type, time periods, or formats. One of the key questions to the modellers was to indicate whether the data required by their tool/model could be generated with other models, could be obtained from available external sources or whether the data was measured or observed data from monitoring instruments. All data that did not require the use of models/tools were requested from the CCS. All this information plays a critical role in ensuring that the data collected is consistent, relevant, and accurate across all modelling tools and sectors.

After gathering all the necessary information from the modelling partners, in T9.2 we analyzed the information provided by the different modelers, in order to generate a uniform and homogeneous data request document. This was done to avoid duplicities of requests and facilitate the data providing task from the CCS partners. The result of this analysis was a table that listed all the data required for the DISTENDER models, which had to be provided by the CCS partners in the next phase of the project, the “Data Collection phase”. See Annex I.

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3 DATA COLLECTING

After the analysis of the data requirements for the DISTENDER models was completed, the next phase of the project was the Data Collection phase. In this phase, the CCS partners were informed about the specific data that they needed to provide to meet the requirements of the DISTENDER models.

The communication of the data requirements was done through a table, see Annex I. The table was accompanied by a descriptive document that provided detailed information on the data that the CCS partners needed to provide. It also provided guidance on how to handle missing data and how to upload the requested files. The communication of the data requirements through the table and the accompanying document was a crucial step in the Data Collection phase, so several meetings were held on the subject to explain in detail the whole data collection procedure to ensure that the CCS partners had a clear understanding of the data that they needed to provide and could begin the process of collecting and preparing the data accordingly. The information provided to the CCS partners regarding the required data is described below.

3.1 Priority levels

In the table of required data (Annex I) there was a column called "priority level" which indicated the degree of relevance of the requested data for the development of the DISTENDER project.

Level 1: highest priority. This data was essential for DISTENDER models/tools and was expected to be provided as soon as possible.

Level 2: medium priority. This data was important for DISTENDER models/tools but not critical. This was asked to be provided throughout the collection period after to deliver the level 1 datasets.

Level 3: low priority. The data was important to get the most benefit from the DISTENDER models/tools in order to obtain very detailed information for the case study. If the CCS have any difficulty in supplying any data at this priority level 3 it would be replaced by more generic data known by the modellers, but taking into account that this reduces the accuracy of the results. The partners from the CCS were asked to make great effort to provide as much data as possible in this category. This data was also expected to be provided throughout the collection period.

The first provided data was the "Geographical boundaries of the case study". This Geographic Information System (GIS) data files defined the geographical area where the case study was going to be developed and on which the partner representing the case study was responsible for providing the rest of the requested data and on which the robust adaptation and mitigation measures were going to be proposed.

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3.2 Groups of data

The requested data was classified into four main categories based on their characteristics, which are explained below.

3.2.1 Geographic data

Geographic data is geo-referenced data of the geographic domain of the case study. This data can be read by Geographic Information Systems (GIS). The partners from the CCS were asked to provide files that include the definition of the geographic projection. The temporal resolution or data frequency was yearly (one data/file every year). There were three types of requested GIS data (raster, vector and point), as it is explained below.

Raster

Raster data is any pixelated (or gridded) data where each pixel is associated with a specific geographical location. The value of a pixel can be continuous (e.g. elevation) or categorical (e.g. land use). The desirable resolution or size of the pixels was 100 m, whilst the minimum required resolution asked was 1 km.

Vector

Vector data structures represent specific features on the Earth's surface and assign attributes to those features. Vectors are composed of discrete geometric locations (x, y values) known as vertices that define the shape of the spatial object. The organization of the vertices determines the type of vector to work with: line or polygon in this context (points are explained in the next section). To illustrate this to the partners from the CCS, we provided them the following example: "a road or a stream may be represented by a line. This line is composed of a series of segments, each "bend" in the road or stream represents a vertex that has defined x, y location. The outlines of survey plot boundaries, lakes, oceans, and states or countries are often represented by polygons". The data category "Geographical boundaries of the case study's" requested to be provided as soon as possible.

Point

Points are vector data where each geographic point is defined by a single x, y coordinate. Examples given of point data included e.g., sampling locations or the location of individual trees.

3.2.2 Observational data

Time series data is a collection of observations obtained through repeated measurements over time. In the DISTENDER the frequency of the data was set to "hourly". The partners from the CCS were requested to include, together with the data, a descriptive file (e.g., measured variables, units, no valid data flag) of the data submitted, including the geographical coordinates and the altitude of each of the measurement points. The data could be formatted in ASCII, csv or Excel formats. The modellers can read the data with the "Readme" file which contains explanation about the datasets.

3.2.3 High level-aggregate data

This corresponds to general or aggregated data for the entire case study (a single value for each requested data). The value could be specific to the case study, to the region where the case study is located or even to the country where the case study is located. The data could be provided in a text file (high-level aggregate data) or in csv, Excel files (numerical data). The frequency of the data requested was yearly.

3.3 Periods

The data described in the previous sections (3.1 and 3.2) was required to represent different time periods. The periods for which data was expected to be provided were specified to the CCS partners. The following periods were defined in DISTENDER for the modelling/simulation tasks:

- Evaluation/Historical period: 1981-2014
- Future period: 2015-2050

Based on these simulation periods, the data request to the CCS was divided into the following time periods:

- **Base year 2014:** this was the highest priority year (i.e., priority 1).
- **Past Period 2015 - 2020:** this was important (i.e., priority 2) for model evaluation activities as it covers the most current past period.
- **Historical Period 1950 – 2015:** this was important for model calibration processes (i.e., priority 3). In case of not having data for the whole period, it was recommended to the partners from the CCS to cover as many years as possible.
- **Future Period 2021-2050:** this corresponds to data projected into the future (i.e., priority 4). In case of not having data for the whole period, it was recommended to cover as many years as possible.

3.4 Data repository

The data was uploaded to the SFTP server of DISTENDER by the partners from the CCS following the guidelines and recommendations outlined in the deliverable D1.2 Data Management Plan I. One of the key recommendations of the Data Management Plan was the use of an SFTP server for storing and sharing data. The SFTP server is a secure file transfer protocol server that allows for the secure transfer of data over a network. It provides an efficient and reliable way to share and store data, which is essential for a project like DISTENDER that involves multiple partners and collaborators. The SFTP server ensured the security of the data and provided a centralized location for partners to access and share the data required for the project. The data is stored in the path DISTENDER/WP9/T9.2/[CASE STUDY FOLDER] in the folder of the corresponding category (1.1 Raster; 1.2 Vector; 1.3 Point; 2. Observational; 3. High Level-Aggregate. (see Figure 4). All uploaded data was accompanied by a **text file (Readme file) describing the data** so that it could be correctly interpreted by the users of the data.

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Figure 3. Structure of the folders of the SFTP DISTENDER.

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4 OTHER DATASETS: CAPITAL AND INDICATORS

These datasets will be used in the T5.7 Risk and Vulnerability (currently ongoing). T5.7 is focused on assessing cross-sectorial risks and vulnerabilities within the case studies following the conceptual model set out by the IPCC (e.g. IPCC, 2014). In this conceptualisation the risk that a case study is exposed to is a factor of three elements: i) **hazard**, the occurrence and severity of a harmful physical event (e.g. a flood); ii) **exposure**, the extent to which the hazard spatially overlays with people or assets of concern (e.g. the people and assets flooded) and iii) differential patterns in **vulnerability**, the sensitivity or susceptibility to harm of those exposed to the hazard (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 4. Overview of DISTENDER approach to impacts and vulnerability in the context of the IPCC risk framework (modified from IPCC, 2014 Fig SPM.1).

In DISTENDER WP5 and WP7 models will take scenario inputs from WP3 (Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios), WP4 (Downscaling climate scenarios) and WP6 (Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies) to produce model runs representing Case Study levels of hazard and exposure to a range of sectoral hazards (e.g. Air Quality, Health, Urban Heat, Energy, Droughts/Floods, impacts on Agriculture, Forestry and other land use). Task 5.7 will develop a methodology that quantifies and spatializes vulnerability by developing spatial layers of **coping capacity** through analysis of contemporary indicators: areas with high coping capacity will have lower vulnerability and vice versa.

This modelling will enable case studies to explicitly consider the fact that different elements of the population the case studies are responsible for will be impacted differently as a factor of both the severity of the hazard they are exposed to and their vulnerability to this hazard due to differential levels of resources available to them.

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Table 1. Definitions of the five capitals and example indicators

Definitions of the five capitals and example indicators
<p>Human capital includes the health, knowledge, skills and motivation of a country's population as well as its individual emotional and spiritual capacities. It characterises the abilities that lie within an individual member of society. It broadly covers areas of education, job experience, skills and health. (Tinch et al., 2017). Human capital Indicators: Previous work (e.g. Dunford et al., 2014; Merkel et al., 2022) have used indicators such as Life expectancy and tertiary education levels to reflect this capital.</p>
<p>Social capital consists of the structures, institutions, networks and relationships of a country's population that enable individuals to maintain and develop their human capital in partnership with others, and to be more productive when working together than in isolation. It includes families, communities, businesses, trade unions, voluntary organisations, legal/political systems and educational and health institutions. Social capital can be used for adaptation by, for example, setting up voluntary organisations for emergency help. It includes informal and often local relationships as well as more formalised ones, like the political regime and civil and political institutions and basically refers to the networks and social relations of people (Tinch et al., 2017). Social capital Indicators: Previous projects have used indicators such as income inequality (as a proxy) and social survey responses around the level of "Help When Threatened" communities feel they would get (Dunford et al., 2014; Merkel et al., 2022).</p>
<p>Financial capital reflects the productive power of the other forms of capital and enables them to be owned and traded (Tinch et al., 2017). Financial capital Indicators: example indicators from other work include income and savings rates (Dunford et al., 2014; Merkel et al., 2022).</p>
<p>Manufactured capital consists of material goods, tools, machines, buildings and other forms of infrastructure that contribute to the production process but do not become embodied in its output. Manufactured capital can be created for adaptation by building dams, water pipelines, sea-walls, hospitals, roads, etc. (Tinch et al, 2017). Manufactured capital Indicators: Previous projects have used indicators such as road network density (calculated by GIS) and variables such as the world bank's produced capital metrics (Dunford et al., 2014; Merkel et al., 2022).</p>
<p>Natural capital consists of natural assets including geology, soil, air, water and all living things. Natural capital underpins the wide range of ecosystem services that are essential to human life and wellbeing. (Tinch et al, 2017). Natural capital Indicators: Natural capital is not a priority for collecting case study inputs for Task 5.7 as the WP5 models will be generating indicators of natural capital using more process-based/statistical models.</p>

To help Task 5.7 quantify and spatialize coping capacity case studies have been asked to help identify and collect indicators following the capitals framework of Porrit et al., (2006). This framework separates resources into human, social, financial, manufactured and natural capitals (Table 1). This has involved iterative discussion between the leads of Task 5.7 and the case studies themselves to scope out indicator datasets for each capital that are available within the cases at a suitable resolution for comparison with the WP5-7 models.

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5 DATA DESCRIPTION

In the context of T9.2, the datasets uploaded by the partners from the CCS were tracked to identify missing or incomplete data during the data collection phase. Specific meetings with CCS partners were conducted to ensure that all required data was collected and uploaded in a timely and efficient manner. The general deadline to upload the data was the 15th of November, 2022.

The status and description of the general (not capitals) uploaded datasets were analyzed, documented and reported in the DISTENER meetings by task leader (UPM) and work package leader (WP9, KVC). A summary table was created for each CCS partner in order to provide a quick overview of the status of the requested data. The summary table used a simple symbol system in which:

- "V": indicated that the requested data had been successfully uploaded by the CCS partner.

"?": meant that the uploaded data was closed to meet the requirements.

"X": indicated that the requested data could not be uploaded because it was not available for the CCS partner. If data was missing, the modellers were responsible for sourcing the data from other available sources.

The next figures show the status of the data uploaded respect to the requested data for the CSS. Figure 6 Geographic data, Figure 7 Observational data, Figure 8 High level-aggregate data.

Capital indicators collecting are ongoing as part of taskT5.7 which is running. These data have had a different deadline than the rest of the data because their use is very specific to the T5.7 task and they will not be used until the end of the WP5 model simulations (end of 2023), Figure 5 shows the current status (31st of May, 2023) of the data collection process for each case study. The final status of the collection of these data will be reported in WP5 deliverables.

		Human	Social	Financial	Manufactured
EURAF (Iberia)	PT	✓✓	✓*	✓*	✓*
	ES	XX	XX	XX	✓X
Turin		*X	XX	✓X	✓*
HUAS (Netherlands)		✓✓	✓*	✓*	✓*
Austria		✓X	✓X	**	✓X
Guimeraes		*X	XX	*X	✓X
✓ Appropriate indicator, appropriate scale, consistent with other papers (e.g. Dunford et al, 2014; Merkel et al., 2022) * Potentially useful data: may need processing / further interpretation. X No data or inappropriate data (wrong scale or incomplete coverage)					

Figure 5. Overview of data collection across capital datasets and case studies within Task 5.7 (as of end May 2023).

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	AUSTRIA	HUAS	EURAF	CMTORINO	GUIMARAES
1. Geographic data (GIS data) - Georeferenced data. Frequently Yearly					
<i>1.1 Raster (100 m desirable or 1 km required)</i>					
Land use and land cover		V	V	V	V
Chemical and physical characteristics of the soil 3D (soil layers)		V	V	V	V
Population density (pax. / ha)	V	V	V	V	V
Areas affected by Spatial planning policies (e.g. protected areas)		?		V	V
Topography (height of the terrain m)	V	V	V	V	V
Permeable paved materials		X		V	
Colour paved materials		X			
Groundwater recharge (mm)		V		V	
Percentage / classes of impervious area or surface kF-value / infiltration capacity		V			
<i>1.2 Vector (polygon or line data)</i>					
<i>Geographical boundaries of the case study</i>					
Roads network (location and type of road)	V	V	V	V	V
Building type (residential, houses, apartments, warehouse, commercial, industrial, retail, office, hospital, etc)		?		V	V
Buildings heights (footprint and height m)		?			
Traffic flow (vehicles/hour, could be point data)	V	V		V	V
Green areas		V	V	V	V
Map of flood risk		V		V	V
River / surface drainage network		V	V	V	V
Sewage and drainage system		?		V	V
Infiltration ditches or structures (maximum infiltration capacity)		?			V
<i>1.3 Point</i>					
Point/industrial emission sources		V		V	
Trees location and type		?		V	V
Hydroengineering structures (dams, weirs, reservoirs, barrages)		V		V	

Figure 6. Current status of the requested geographic data for each CCS (as of end May 2023).

	AUSTRIA	HUAS	EURAF	CMTORINO	GUIMARAES
2. Observational data (measurements, point time series, csv-excell + location coordinates and altitude) - Hourly					
Meteorological data (temperature, wind, precipitation, humidity, pressure, shortwave radiation)	V	V	V	V	V
Air quality data (NO2, CO, O3, PM10, PM2.5) (ug/m3)	V	V		V	V
Flow volume (runoff) at river gauge (m3/s)		V		V	V
Water level at river gauge (cm)		V			
Soil moisture (m3/m3)		?			
Surface water extraction or diversion (m3/s)		V		V	
Groundwater extraction (m3/s)		V		V	
Storage volume of dams and reservoirs (m3)		V			
Height of dams / levees (m)		V			

Figure 7. Current status of the requested observations data for each CCS (as of end May 2023).

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	AUSTRIA	HUAS	EURAF	CNTORINO	GUIMARAES
3. Narrative and Aggregate data (one data for all case study, local, regional or national), txt, csv, excel – Yearly					
Population (total number of people)		V		V	V
Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (€)		V		V	V
Fleet composition (vehicles/ vehicle categories)		V		V	
Population data by age groups		V		V	V
Mortality rate due to all causes or by cause (%)	V	V		V	V
Rules applied to manage a reservoir (max volume/height, temporal rules, usual runoff)		X			
Crop management (planting, harvest, irrigation applications, nutrient applications, pesticide applications, and tillage operations)		V		V	
Water price (€/l)		V		V	
SVL – Statistical value of life (€)		X		V	
Water salinity (ppt)		V			V
Health statistics by age, sex, (mental, heart, respiratory disease, respiratory mortality,		V		V	
Passenger transport demand by transport mode (pkm)		V		V	
Freight transport demand by transport mode (tkm)		V		V	
Final demand expenditure shares (%)		X			
Electricity generation cost (%)		V		V	V
Fossil fuel prices		V		V	V
Wastewater production, collection, treatment and re-use (ml)		V		V	V
Flood risk average economic cost (M€/y)		X			
Water system cost: Operational and maintenance s and Investment in water systems (M€/y)		V		V	
Water demand per sector (Domestic, Industrial, Livestock, Irrigation)	V	V		V	V
Water resource availability (Groundwater and Surface)		V		V	
Policy decription regarding energy production and demand.		V		V	
Energy consumption (MWh) of the private sector industry, agriculture and buildings	V	V		V	V
Public Building Energy Consumption and Public Lighting Data (MWh or GJ) by Fuel Type		V/ X		V	
Daily Non-resident Commuters		X		V	
District energy demand		V		V	
Proportion (%) of Residents in City with Electricity Service				V	
Streetlight and trafficligh Data (consumption, average hours operation per day, percentage of leds)		V/ X		V	
Electricity Generation Mix (solar, wind, hydroelectric,geothermal, biomass, nuclear, natural gas, propane gas, coal,LPG,....) for Grid-Supplied Power (MWh and %)		V		V	
Emission Factor (t / KWh (CO2; CH4; N2O; etc) for electricity supplied or other fuels		V		V	
Solid Waste data (Total Solid Waste Tonnage, Proportion of Organic Waste, Anaerobic Digester Biogas		V			V
Energy - Water Conveyance Energy Data (Total Annual Water Consumption, Water Supply Loss Data, %		V		V	
Transportation Data (Passenger Trips per Capita per Year, Split % Between Passenger and Freight Transport, Total Vehicle Kilometers Travelled (VKT), Average Trip Length, Passenger Mode Share)		V			
Energy - Discount Rate (%)		V			
Energy - Wholesale Cost of Water (€/m3)		X		V	
Energy Costs (Electricity Rates and Fuel Prices by each type of fuel) (€/kWh)		V		V	
Rules applied to manage a reservoir (max volume/height, temporal rules, usual runoff)		X			

Figure 8. Current status of the requested high level-aggregate data for each CCS (as of end May 2023).

Below is more detailed information on the data uploaded by each CCS partner corresponding to the data described in the previous sections of the document. All the CCS were asked for the same data, but each CCS has provided different data due to the specificities of each CCS, it should be taken into account that in the project there are CCS of different scales, national, regional and urban, which also influences the access to the data. The text below has been extracted from the Readme files provided by the CCS partners for each dataset uploaded.

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5.1 Austria (BMK)

5.1.1 Geographic data

- Population density from 2011 to 2022.
- Topography or height of the terrain: the digital terrain model was obtained from the national datasets catalog ⁽¹⁾. It is a digital terrain model from airborne laser scan data. Elevation data of the terrain in a grid of 10m x 10m. The digital surface model, Obtained from the national dataset catalog ⁽²⁾. The Digital Surface Model (DSM) describes the earth's surface including all objects located on it in the form of point sets, which are arranged in a regular grid and georeferenced in position and height. In contrast to the digital terrain model (DTM), the vegetation and built-up surface is thus represented.
- Road network: the Graph Integration Platform Austria (GIP) is Austria's intermodal, official traffic reference system. The dataset contains the following sub-datasets:
 - A - Routing export: one IDF total file, ZIP archive with the individual IDF tables split up.
 - B - GIP Network = basic network: sections, nodes, links, usage strips, turn-off relations.
 - C - Geopackage GIP Reference: objects of the export that reference the GIP base network: "Brunnel" layer, "Reference Points" layer, "Bikeroutes" layer, "Geoname" layer.
 - D - Lookup tables.
- Traffic flow from 2012 to 2021: the data is obtained from ASFINAG ⁽³⁾. ASFINAG carries out traffic counts on the freeway and expressway network in order to observe and record the long-term development of traffic. Automatic permanent counting stations are mainly used for this purpose.
- Land use data.

(1) <https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/b5de6975-417b-4320-afdb-eb2a9e2a1dbf>.

(2) https://www.bev.gv.at/portal/page?_pageid=713,2875611&_dad=portal&_schema=PORTAL

(3) <https://www.asfinag.at/verkehr-sicherheit/verkehrszahlung/>

5.1.2 Observational data

- Meteorological data from 1950 to 2022: air pressure, air temperature, precipitation and wind speed. 24 hourly values of a specific parameter are displayed on daily basis. The ZAMG (Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik) ⁽¹⁾ station network comprises about 260 automatic measuring stations. The measuring stations of ZAMG cover all climatic regions and altitudes of Austria. The quality status of individual days can be seen from the quality flag "qflag". The data was split up into yearly as the download size is limited. The combined data set can be obtained from ZAMG via API.

(1) <https://data.hub.zamg.ac.at/dataset/klima-v1-1h>.

5.1.3 High level-aggregate data

- Population by age: population 2021-2051.
- Mortality rate: mortality rates 2021-2050.
- Water demand by sector: water resource availability (Groundwater and Surface) and Water demand per sector ⁽¹⁾ (Domestic, Industrial, Livestock, Irrigation).
- Energy: energy consumption (MWh) of the private sector industry, agriculture and buildings.
- Public building energy consumption and public lighting data (MWh or Gj) by fuel type.
- Emission Factor (t / KWh for CO₂; CH₄; N₂O) for electricity supplied or other fuels.

(1) <https://info.bml.gv.at/themen/wasser/nutzung-wasser/wasserschatz-oesterreichs-studie.htm>

5.1.4 Capital and indicators

- Austria has provided a number of datasets, however not all have been at a sufficiently high spatial resolution (NUTS3 or, ideally, below).
- Work to collect datasets is ongoing.
- Data that is currently available includes: proportion of population with tertiary education (H) and median gross pay (F) at District level from. Data is also available on total employment (F) at NUTS3 as well as data from which road networks can be calculated (M).

5.2 North-East of The Netherlands (HUAS)

5.2.1 Geographic data

- Chemical and physical characteristics of the soil 3D: data soil characteristics (clay content, sand content, nitrogen, Ph., carbon and soil groups).
- Land use and land cover: 500 meters resolution dataset of land-use in GML format.
- Population density 2017-2022: Map of 100 meters by 100 meters with statistics on the Netherlands.
- Topography: DTM (Digital Terrain Model) files with a 0.5-meter raster on the height of the terrain. The data has been collected between 2014-2019.
- Impervious area: this file was compiled on behalf of the 12 provinces, with the aim of indicating within which rural areas of the Dutch provinces there is a risk of subsoil compaction and in which areas there is not.
- Building heights: this data was compiled in 3D. 3D is a digital topographical file with three-dimensional objects. The file is based on topography from the Basisregistratie Grootschalige Topografie (BGT), the buildings from the Basisregistratie Adressen en Gebouwen (BAG), and fully automatic height generation from aerial photo images

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and the Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland (current altitude file of the Netherlands). Basisvoorziening 3D can be used at scales between 1:500 and 1:10.000.

- Green areas: Natura2000 Areas (protected, green areas). The hectares of forest, open natural areas, parks and allotment gardens for the year 2015 for the specific region of the CS.
- River surface drainage network: hydro object/Surface water body - Bank - Profile defense - Water storage area - Water Section The data is structured according to the Water Information Model (IMWA), part of the Aquo standard. The data is delivered in Geopackage format in the RD-New coordinate system. The data comes from the individual water boards, but is delivered via PDOK as a single national coverage file. The file thus contains the entire Netherlands, and not only the CS region.
- Road network: vector dataset with information on road type, max speed and other data.
- Traffic flow: traffic flow information for 2014 - 2018, monthly data.
- Industrial emission sources: national data for location industry and CO₂ emissions from 2005 – 2010.
- Hydro engineering structures.

5.2.2 Observational data

- Air quality data: data for 2014 - 2020 (monthly) for NO₂, O₃, PM₁₀. PM_{2.5}.
- Flow volume (runoff) at river gauge.
- Meteorological data: 1950-2015, 2014, 2015-2020. Data from weather stations located within the region: humidity, precipitation, pressure, shortwave radiation, temperature and wind.
- Groundwater data: the groundwater level survey registration object includes measurements of the variation in the level of groundwater discharged into a known groundwater monitoring well with a certain pipe. The monitoring data provide insight into the response of groundwater to changes such as the lowering of a polder level, or groundwater extraction.
- Surface water extraction.

5.2.3 High level-aggregate data

- Population (total number of people) 2014 – 2050: data on the total number of people for the three provinces that make up the CS, as well as the total of the Netherlands.
- Energy costs 1990 - 2021: the consumer price index (CPI) energy reflects the price development of natural gas and electricity consumption by households.
- Gross Domestic Product (GDP): GDP (in million euros) for the CS region from the year 1995 onwards.
- Water demand per sector 1995 - 2020: water use by companies and private households; national accounts. Water use by the Dutch economy. The water use (including leakage loss) is the combination of 'water extracted/produced and used by itself added to the amount produced and supplied by others', for the distinguished types of water in the table.

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- Water level at river gauge.
- Water price: water price in The Netherlands is determined per water company. Average price for 2019 and 2020 for the whole of the Netherlands.
- Fossil fuel prices: fossil fuel prices for cars from the 1st of January, 2006 –until the 17th of October, 2022, for euro95, LPG (Liquefied Petroleum Gas), and diesel types of fuels. World oil price. Coal price and gas price.
- Mortality rate: number of deceased and the total number of people at the beginning of a period for the CS-region.
- Population data by age groups: average population data per year, and have been divided in men, women, and total.
- Crop management: agriculture; crops, animals and land use by region. Region-level data on land use, arable farming, horticulture, grassland, grazing animals and farm animals. For all subjects, both the census data (area, number of animals), and the corresponding number of farms are presented. Plant protection products; marketing active substance, application groups.
- District energy demand: energy consumption private dwellings; dwelling type per municipality within the CS region from the years 2010 – 2021.
- Electricity generation cost: data for costs of electricity and gas monthly for 1996 – 2022.
- Electricity generation mix: supply, transformation and consumption. Year 1950 – 2021.
- Emission factor: CO₂ emission factors for fuels, energy carriers, transport movements and refrigerants from 2015 – 2022.
- Energy - discount rate: In the Netherlands, one is entitled to the energy allowance of about €1.300 (price depended on what you earn) if you: earn less than €1,310.05 (single) or €1,871.50 (cohabiting) net per month. If you receive such a benefit, you will automatically receive the energy allowance from your municipality.
- Energy - water conveyance energy data: energy balance supply and consumption overview in The Netherlands. Water use by businesses and private households
- Energy consumption: energy consumption by sector, 1990-2019. Energy balance; supply and consumption, sector.
- Fleet composition: motor vehicles; type, 2014-2022. Data on the vehicle fleet of passenger cars, motorcycles and commercial vehicles (by vehicle category) and by age class of the vehicle.
- Freight transport demand: data on total vehicle kilometers of goods vehicles in the Netherlands (broken down by Dutch and foreign vehicles) and data of total kilometers and average annual kilometers of Dutch goods vehicles (broken down by Dutch and foreign territory).
- Health statistics: five variants of health expectancies: life expectancy in perceived good health, life expectancy without physical limitations, life expectancy without chronic morbidity, life expectancy in good mental health and life expectancy without GALI-limitations.
- Passenger transport demand: total transport performance in the Netherlands; modes of travel for three provinces of the CS region. Information regarding the mobility of

the residents of the Netherlands aged 6 or older in private households, so excluding residents of institutions and homes. The table contains the total number of passenger kilometers travelled on Dutch territory including kilometers travelled during series of calls trips and domestic holiday mobility. The distance travelled is based on stage information.

- Policy description energy: policy regarding energy in the Netherlands. ⁽¹⁾
- Public building energy consumption and public lighting data: public lighting for the municipality of Assen (in the province of Drenthe) and the municipality of Sudwest-Fryslan (in the province of Friesland).
- Solid waste: information on the amount of municipal waste, broken down by type of waste and method of disposal.
- Streetlight and traffic light.
- Transportation data: traffic performance motor vehicles; kilometers, type of vehicle, territory, for the whole of the Netherlands. Mobility; per person, trip characteristics, travel purposes and region for 2018 - 2021 (one file per year). Vehicle kilometers goods vehicles; kilometers, load capacity, territory for whole of the NL.
- Wastewater: urban wastewater treatment.
- Water resource availability: data on different types of surface waters (lakes, rivers, canals, etc..) in 2009 for the whole of the Netherlands.
- Water salinity.
- Water system cost: total cost of protecting the Netherlands from flooding and ensure sufficient and clean (drinking) water.

(1) <https://www.iea.org/countries/the-netherlands>

5.2.4 Capital and indicators

- The Netherlands case study has delivered indicators for the majority of capitals. Work is still needed to check them but T5.7 has data for two indicators per capital.
- These indicators include municipality level data for: life expectancy (H), education level (H), “perceived health” (H), variables from which income inequality can be calculated (S), statistics on crime (S), social support (S), household income (F), wealth (F), employment rate (F) and information from which road networks can be assessed (M) as well as proximity data for a range of facilities such as hospitals, GPs etc (M).
- Further work is needed to interrogate the data and ensure fitness for purpose but the initial Netherlands data looks very promising and appropriate for the task

5.3 South-West of the Iberian Peninsula (EURAF)

5.3.1 Geographic data

- Land use data: Corine Land Cover (CLC) Spain and Portugal 2012-2016-2018:
- Topography: Model digital Terrain, source SRTM.
- Green Areas (Nature 2000).
- Population: population and habitation census of 2011.

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- River Network.
- Road Network.
- Soil.
- Emission sources.

5.3.2 Observational data

- Water level rivers reservoirs subterranean.
- Air Quality 2014-2021: Extremadura and Portugal. SO₂, NO₂, NO, CO, O₃; PM₁₀. PM_{2.5}
- Meteorological data.

5.3.3 High level-aggregate data

- Crop management.
- Electricity generation cost.
- Emission Factor.
- Energy consumption.
- Energy costs output prices.
- Energy social discount rate.
- Energy Water consumption supply loss.
- Final demand expenditure shares.
- Fleet composition 2014-2020: Ávila, Extremadura, Madrid and Toledo.
- Flood risk cost.
- Fossil fuel prices: for light fuel oil for households, automotive diesel, unleaded premium (95 RON) gasoline and automotive LPG, end-use prices are, from 1Q2009 onwards, based on retail prices reported by about 3 000 filling stations throughout continental Portugal, available at www.precoscombustiveis.dgeg.gov.pt.
- Freight transport demand.
- GDP.
- Health statistics.
- Mortality rate causes 2014-2020.
- Passenger transport demand.
- Policy description regarding energy production and demand.
- Población 2014-2021: Ávila, Badajoz, Cáceres, Madrid, Portugal, Salamanca y Toledo.
- Population age groups.
- Public Building Energy Consumption and public.
- Solid Waste data.
- Transportation Data.
- Value of life 2014 – 2022.
- Wastewater production, collection, treatment and re-use (ml).
- Water demand per sector.

- Water prices: evolution of price by region from year 2000 to 2016, and average price per region in Euros/m³.
- Water resource availability.
- Water system cost.

5.3.4 Capital and indicators

- The Portuguese (PT) side of the case study is well represented. A range of municipal level datasets have been collected for Portugal. These include both health and education (H); income inequality (S); income, earnings, pensions (F); and road networks and number of hospitals (M).
- Spanish data (ES) is a priority for collection. Existing data is incomplete or at too coarse a resolution (NUTS 3). Municipal level data is preferred. However, information from which road networks (M) could be calculated is available.

5.4 Guimaraes (Portugal)

5.4.1 Geographic data

- Areas affected by Spatial planning policies: a biophysical structure that integrates the set of areas that, due to their ecological value and sensitivity or their exposure and subset to natural hazards, are objects of special protection. It is a public utility restriction, to which a special territorial regime is applied that establishes a set of conditions for the occupation, use and transformation of the soil, identifying the uses and actions defined with the objectives of this regime in the various types of areas.
- Land use and land cover: land Use and Occupancy Mapping (COS). The COS is a national product with a minimum cartographic unit of 1 ha and a minimum distance between lines of 20 meters and constitutes a time series with five reference years (1995, 2007, 2010, 2015 and 2018). COS nomenclature is fully compatible with CORINE Land Cover nomenclature.
- Population density.
- Topography (height of the terrain m).
- Building type.
- Building heights: calculated building heights.
- Green areas.
- Infiltration ditches or structures (maximum infiltration capacity): maximum infiltration areas.
- Map of flood risk: flood zones are considered to be areas hit by the highest flood.
- River surface drainage network.
- Road network.
- Sewage and drainage system.
- Soil type.
- Study area.
- Traffic flow.

- Tree location and type.

5.4.2 Observational data

- Air quality data.
- Hydrological data.
- Meteorological data.

5.4.3 High level-aggregate data

- Electricity Generation Mix.
- Energy consumption (MWh) of the private sector industry, agriculture and buildings: data downloaded from The Directorate-General for Energy and Geology (DGEG).
- Fossil Fuel Prices.
- Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (€).
- Health statistics by age, sex, (mental, heart, respiratory diseases, respiratory mortality): mortality rate (30 to 70 years old) attributed to diseases of the circulatory system, malignant tumors, diabetes mellitus and chronic respiratory diseases per 100 000 inhabitants.
- Mortality rate (%).
- Population data by age groups.
- Population (total number of people).
- Solid Waste Data: waste from dwellings as well as other waste that, due to its composition or characteristics, is similar to that produced in dwellings. Set of equipment and associated operations that are implemented with the objective of guaranteeing an adequate final destination for the waste produced by the population of one or more population clusters.
- Waste water production, collection, treatment and re-use (ml): drained wastewater and source of wastewater. Wastewater drained per inhabitant; Yearly Wastewater treated in wastewater treatment plants.
- Water demand per Origin (Surface Water, Groundwater)
- Water salinity: physical-chemical parameters.

5.4.4 Capital and indicators

- Partners from Guimaraes have provided a lot of datasets, many of which have been really helpful in populating the variables for the Portuguese side of the Iberian case study.
- However, it has been challenging to identify datasets at the high resolution (e.g. Parish / sub-parish) that would be most suitable for the Guimaraes case study. Work to identify datasets is ongoing.
- Datasets available: population by age group from which dependency ratios could perhaps be calculated (H), ratio between rented and owned properties (F), data from which road networks (M) and proximity to important assets can be calculated (M).

5.5 Metropolitan City of Turin (CMTo)

5.5.1 Geographic data

- Land use and cover: land use and land cover information associated with geometries from the regional geo-topographic database (BDTRE). The attributes are organized according to the project classifications Piedmont Land Cover.
- Chemical data soli: soil characteristics.
- Population density.
- Area affected by spatial plan policies.
- Topography.
- Groundwater recharge: deep aquifer recharge areas - scale 1: 250.000
- Impervious area: soil drainage capacity. Protective capacity of soils against groundwater. Waterproofed soils. The information relating to the capacity of the soils (drainage and protective) does not take into account already urbanized surfaces, therefore in consideration of the use that must be made of them, it is necessary to evaluate whether to cut out such data taking into account the waterproofed surfaces
- Vulnerability surface aquifer: Intrinsic vulnerability of the surface aquifer, assessed basing on the following factors: G = degree of confinement of the aquifer; O = lithological characteristics and degree of cohesion of the rocks of the unsaturated area (for non-confined aquifers) and of the neighboring roof levels (for confined aquifers) D = subsidence of the free surface aquifer in the case of an unconfined aquifer or aquifer roof for confined aquifers.
- Catchment areas: catchment area, territory in which all surface waters flow through a series of streams, rivers and possibly lakes to flow into the sea at a single mouth, estuary or delta. Hydrographic sub-basin: territory in which all surface waters flow through a series of streams, rivers and possibly lakes to flow into a single section in a higher-order water body. Hydrographic area: portion of the territory into which a hydrographic sub-basin is divided, functional to the implementation and which for some hydrographic sub-basins coincides with the sub-basin itself.
- Roads and net traffic low: the arcs of the roads monitored by the CMTo and the traffic and speed data. Average Daily Traffic, number of vehicles that average daily transit on the road element in the reference year.
- Building type.
- Green areas: data from the BDTRE (Territorial Data Base of Reference of Bodies) which describes the arboreal or shrub or floristic-herbaceous formations, including forest species, vegetating in parks, gardens, botanical gardens, and in general in any situation in which the plant formation had exclusive aesthetic purposes or in any case different from agroforestry ones, as well as trees in rows in an agricultural and road environment. These are the green areas for ornamental purposes or inserted in recreational areas. The areas of flower beds, gardens, lawns, wooded areas inserted in the urban area for use or even private gardens belong to this class.
- Flood risk maps.
- River surface drainage.
- Sewage drainage: aqueducts and sewerage.

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- Industrial emission: the estimates concern the sources classified according to the SNAP nomenclature (Selected Nomenclature for Air Pollution) and refer to the pollutants: methane (CH₄), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O), ammonia (NH₃), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), fine dust with a diameter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}).
- Tree location and types.
- Hydrogen strut: reservoirs and small dams, reservoir for flood lamination and ravers.

5.5.2 Observational data

- Meteorological data: historical data is provided on a daily basis for all the monitoring station available in CHRO domain for the following parameters: Precipitation from 9 to 9 hours (mm); Precipitation from 0 to 0 hours (mm); Fresh Snow (cm); Ground Snow (cm); Snow Maximum Height (cm); Temperature average (°C); Temperature max (°C); Temperature min (°C); Humidity average (%); Humidity average (%); Humidity min (%); Wind speed average (m/s).
- Air quality data: data is reported for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, NO₂, CO.
- Flow volume at river gauge (water level): data is referred on flow rate of the main rivers within the different basin.
- Surface water extraction.
- Groundwater extraction: the flow rate expressed in l/sec represents the average concession flow rate (fixed for the entire duration of the concession) calculated by dividing the maximum volume granted during the calendar year by the time period in which the drawdown is authorized (irrigation tends to be granted in the April-September irrigation season).
- Dams reservoir volume height: a list of infrastructures of national competence, of the whole region. There are various data of height, volumes, etc.

5.5.3 High level-aggregate data

- Population.
- GDP.
- Vehicle fleet.
- Population by age.
- Mortality.
- Agricultural.
- Water prices: state fees related to public water use and related minimum amounts for each type of use.
- SVL (Statistical Value of Life)
- Health statistic: data from the National Statistical Institute (ISTAT) from 2009 to 2020. divided by males and females and by type of disease.
- Passenger transport: air transport (referred to the Sandro Pertini airport which is located in the municipality of Caselle Torinese, in CMT) 2014-2020 Rail transport (2017-2020) Road transport - goods transported.

- Freight transport.
- Electricity generation cost.
- Fossil fuel price.
- Wastewater.
- Water system cost.
- Water demand.
- Water resource availability: data on the volume of water captured (m³/year) from wells and springs.
- Policy.
- Energy Consumption.
- Public building energy consumption.
- Daily commuter: the data was those collected by the National Statistical Institute (ISTAT) during the official censuses. The data refers to income for study and work, for the years 1991, 2001, 2011.
- District energy demand: the main information (served volumetric and delivered energy) for all the district heating networks operating in the CMO Territory. Data is provided for 2014, 2021 and 2022.
- Population resident with electricity: 100%
- Streetlight and traffic light data.
- Electricity generation.
- Emission factor: CO₂ - national emission factors of electricity production and electricity consumption (g CO₂ / kWh). CH₄-N₂O - greenhouse gas emission factors from the electricity sector for the production of electricity and heat (g CO₂eq / kWh)
- Other - national emission factors of atmospheric pollutants emitted by the electricity sector for the production of electricity and heat (mg / kWh).
- Energy water conveyance energy data: water introduced into the aqueduct network. Water delivered to users. Estimation of time wasters.
- Cost of water: the rates applied included: access fee independent of drinking water consumption; variable tariff proportional to the consumption of drinking water measured and divided into increasing price ranges; fee for the sewage service; tariff for the purification of waste water. The last two tariffs are proportionate according to the consumption of drinking water. The tariff of the water supply service is differentiated according to the type of use (e.g. domestic, agricultural, public, industrial) and by territorial bands, determined in relation to the altitude and socio-economic marginality. The rate of the wastewater treatment service is differentiated according to the type of use, civil or productive. For productive use, coefficients related to the quality and quantity of the discharged water are applied. There are also tariff reductions for families based on the equivalent economic situation.
- Energy cost.
- Crop Management.

5.5.4 Capital and indicators

- The Turin case study has provided a number of datasets, however not all have been at a resolution useable within Task 5.7 due to differences in spatial resolution or not being quite the right indicator.
- Work to collect datasets is ongoing. Municipal level data is available for taxable income (F) internet access (M) and road network indicators (M) can be calculated.
- Solutions still need to be found with respect to additional datasets for Financial and Manufactured capitals and to provide usable data for Human and Social Capital

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Conclusions

The successful implementation of any modelling task relies on the availability and accuracy of the required input data. In the context of the DISTENDER project, a comprehensive effort was made to ensure that the modelling partners had access to the necessary data to effectively run their models and tools. This process involved the careful analysis and consolidation of data requests made by the modelling partners, which was carried out by the T9.2 team. CCS partners have made a huge effort to supply the required data.

The modelling partners were asked to specify the data required to run their models and tools effectively. The data requested by the modelling partners were analyzed to generate a uniform and homogeneous data request without duplication. All data needed by the models and tools of DISTENDER were supplied by the CCS, and the missing data was substituted with alternative known sources of the modelling partners. As a result of T9.2, all the minimum data requested for the modelling tasks in work packages WP4, WP5 and WP7 were provided.

The successful implementation of the T9.2 allowed the modelling partners to have the necessary data to start their simulations. The data (provided by CCS and provided by the modelers) was stored in the DISTENDER SFTP server, following the recommendations of the Data Management Plan I to promote information exchange between partners. The deliverable D9.2 was then produced to report the successful closure of the T9.2 task.

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ANNEX I

	Priority Level	Historical Period 1950 - 2015 (3)	Base year 2014 (1)	Past Period 2015 - 2020 (2)	Future Period 2021-2050 (4)	More information
1. Geographic data (GIS data) - Georeferenced data. Frequently Yearly						
1.1 Raster (100 m desirable or 1 km required)						
Land use and land cover	1	x	x	x	x	The most detailed classification available (e.g. Corineair).
Chemical and physical characteristics of the soil 3D (soil layers)	1		x			Soil depth, pH, texture (% sand,% silt, % clay) , Soil Organic Matter
Population density (pax. / ha)	1		x	x	x	
Areas affected by Spatial planning policies (e.g. protected areas)	2		x	x	x	
Topography (height of the terrain m)	1		x			
Permeable paved materials	3					
Color paved materials	3		x	x	x	
Groundwater recharge (mm)	3	x	x	x		
Percentage / classes of impervious area or surface kF-value / infiltration capacity	2	x	x	x	x	Could be a vector file
1.2 Vector (polygon or line data)						
<u>Geographical boundaries of the case study</u>	1		x			
Roads network (location and type of road)	1		x			

Building type (residential, houses, apartments, warehouse, commercial, industrial, retail, office, hospital, educational, hotel, public...)	2	x	x	x	x	
Buildings heights (footprint and height m)	1		x	x	x	
Traffic flow (vehicles/hour, could be point data)	2		x	x	x	
Green areas	1		x	x	x	
Map of flood risk	2	x	x	x	x	
River / surface drainage network	1		x	x	x	
Sewage and drainage system	2	x	x	x	x	Available information on network, flow capacities, manholes, outfalls, inlets, pipe diameter, etc.
Infiltration ditches or structures (maximum infiltration capacity)	2	x	x	x	x	
1.3 Point						
Point/industrial emission sources	2		x	x	x	Location of industrial sites, emissions measurements, stack properties
Trees location and type	2		x	x	x	Could be a polygonal data
Hydro engineering structures (dams, weirs, reservoirs, barrages)	2		x	x	x	
2. Observational data (measurements, point time series, csv-excell + location coordinates and altitude) - Hourly						
Meteorological data (temperature, wind, precipitation, humidity, pressure, shortwave radiation)	1	x	x	x		
Air quality data (NO ₂ , CO, O ₃ , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5}) (ug/m ³)	1		x	x		

Flow volume (runoff) at river gauge (m3/s)	1	x	x	x		All points within the catchment, that contains the case study area
Water level at river gauge (cm)	2	x	x	x		All points within the catchment, that contains the case study area
Soil moisture (m3/m3)	3	x	x	x		All points within the catchment, that contains the case study area
Surface water extraction or diversion (m3/s)	2		x	x	x	All points within the catchment, that contains the case study area
Groundwater extraction (m ³ /s)	2		x	x	x	All points within the catchment, that contains the case study area
Storage volume of dams and reservoirs (m3)	2		x	x	x	All points within the catchment, that contains the case study area
Height of dams / levees (m)	2		x	x	x	
3. High level-aggregate and Aggregate data (one data for all case study, local, regional or national), txt, csv, excel - Yearly						
Population (total number of people)	1		x	x	x	
Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (€)	2	x	x	x	x	
Fleet composition (vehicles/ vehicle categories)	3		x	x	x	
Population data by age groups	3		x	x	x	
Mortality rate due to all causes or by cause (%)	3		x	x	x	
Rules applied to manage a reservoir (max volume/height, temporal rules, usual runoff)	3		x	x	x	
Crop management (planting, harvest, irrigation applications, nutrient applications, pesticide applications, and tillage operations)	3		x	x	x	
Water price (€/l)	2		x	x	x	

SVL - Statistical value of life (€)	3		x	x		Monetary value of a life lost - at least country specific, if available
Water salinity (ppt)	3	x	x	x	x	Salinity is measured indirectly by testing the electrical conductivity (EC) of the water.
Health statistics by age, sex, (mental, heart, respiratory disease, respiratory mortality,	3		x	x		
Passenger transport demand by transport mode (pkm)	3	x	x	x	x	
Freight transport demand by transport mode (tkm)	3	x	x	x	x	
Final demand expenditure shares (%)	3	x	x	x	x	
Electricity generation cost (%)	3	x	x	x	x	differentiated for electricity generation technologies
Fossil fuel prices	3	x	x	x	x	differentiated for coal, oil, gas
Wastewater production, collection, treatment and re-use (ml)	2		x			
Flood risk average economic cost (M€/y)	2	x	x	x	x	
Water system cost: Operational and maintenance s and Investment in water systems (M€/y)	2		x	x	x	
Water demand per sector (Domestic, Industrial, Livestock, Irrigation)	2		x	x	x	
Water resource availability (Groundwater and Surface)	2		x	x	x	
Policy description regarding energy production and demand.	2	x	x	x	x	
Energy consumption (MWh) of the private sector industry, agriculture and buildings	2	x	x	x	x	Please provide a breakdown in terms of energy source.
Public Building Energy Consumption and Public Lighting Data (MWh or Gj) by Fuel Type	2	x	x	x	x	
Daily Non-resident Commuters	3	x	x	x	x	

District energy demand	2	x	x	x	x	Please provide a breakdown in terms of energy source and users
Proportion (%) of Residents in City with Electricity Service	2	x	x	x	x	
Streetlight and traffic light Data (consumption, average hours operation per day, percentage of leds)	3	x	x	x	x	
Electricity Generation Mix (solar, wind, hydroelectric, geothermal, biomass, nuclear, natural gas, propane gas, coal, LPG,....) for Grid-Supplied Power (MWh and %)	3	x	x	x	x	Please estimate what amount and percentage of the grid-supplied electricity comes from each of the specified sources. Note that these percentages refer solely to electricity provided by the grid rather than distributed generation within the city/region boundary. To the extent possible, please provide locally-specific information and ensure the mix sums to 100%. If this is unavailable use national-level proxies.
Emission Factor (t / KWh (CO ₂ ; CH ₄ ; N ₂ O; etc.) for electricity supplied or other fuels	2	x	x	x	x	
Solid Waste data (Total Solid Waste Tonnage, Proportion of Organic Waste, Anaerobic Digester Biogas End Use and Incineration Heat Energy End Use)	3	x	x	x	x	
Energy - Water Conveyance Energy Data (Total Annual Water Consumption, Water Supply Loss Data, Water Supply - Fuel Type)	3	x	x	x	x	
Transportation Data (Passenger Trips per Capita per Year, Split % Between Passenger and Freight Transport, Total Vehicle Kilometers Travelled (VKT), Average Trip Length, Passenger Mode Share)	3	x	x	x	x	

Energy - Discount Rate (%)	2	x	x	x	x	Please state the social discount rate appropriate for your city or country's growth levels. The discount rate will be used to conduct financial forecasts.
Energy - Wholesale Cost of Water (€/m3)	2	x	x	x	x	
Energy Costs (Electricity Rates and Fuel Prices by each type of fuel) (€/kWh)	2	x	x	x	x	Please provide information on the electricity rates by end user in terms of € per kWh. Proxy data is available, typically at a national level, if needed. Residential Electricity. Commercial Electricity Municipal Electricity Industrial Electricity Transportation Electricity.
Rules applied to manage a reservoir (max volume/height, temporal rules, usual runoff)	2		x	x	x	
Management per crop (planting, harvest, irrigation applications)	3		x	x	x	
4. Data to be obtained from Co-creation process during the project						
2x Human Capital Indicators (to be decided by case - e.g. health and education)						The intention is to work with the case studies to identify appropriate indicators of adaptive/coping capacity drawing on the availability of natural, financial, manufactured, human and social capital. These capitals will be derived from available indicators at the case study level (e.g. health statistics, education data etc.) It may be that some of the variables requested by other modelers will serve this purpose also.

<p>2x Social Capital Indicators (to be decided by case - e.g. inequality, trust, collaboration)</p>					<p>The intention is to work with the case studies to identify appropriate indicators of adaptive/coping capacity drawing on the availability of natural, financial, manufactured, human and social capital. These capitals will be derived from available indicators at the case study level (e.g. health statistics, education data etc.) It may be that some of the variables requested by other modelers will serve this purpose also.</p>
<p>2x Financial Capital Indicators (to be decided by case - e.g. savings and income)</p>					<p>The intention is to work with the case studies to identify appropriate indicators of adaptive/coping capacity drawing on the availability of natural, financial, manufactured, human and social capital. These capitals will be derived from available indicators at the case study level (e.g. health statistics, education data etc.) It may be that some of the variables requested by other modelers will serve this purpose also.</p>
<p>2x Manufactured Capital Indicators (to be decided by case - e.g. produced capital, infrastructure, road networks)</p>					<p>The intention is to work with the case studies to identify appropriate indicators of adaptive/coping capacity drawing on the availability of natural, financial, manufactured, human and social capital. These capitals will be derived from available indicators at the case study level (e.g. health statistics, education data etc.) It may be that some of the variables requested by other modelers will serve this purpose also.</p>

<p>2x Natural Capital Indicators (to be decided by case - likely to derive from DISTENDER model outputs e.g. land use change, water availability etc.)</p>					<p>The intention is to work with the case studies to identify appropriate indicators of adaptive/coping capacity drawing on the availability of natural, financial, manufactured, human and social capital. These capitals will be derived from available indicators at the case study level (e.g. health statistics, education data etc.) It may be that some of the variables requested by other modelers will serve this purpose also.</p>
<p>Mitigation policy parameter</p>					<p>Mitigation policy can be either implemented as technological change or via emission pricing. Dataset should include: i) relative change with respect to baseline of economic flows (OPEX and CAPEX) and stocks (e.g. capital stock, labor force) of relevant economic</p>

